

A Review of Devices for Communication Between Dogs and Their Owners

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ABSTRACT

The goal of the increasing number of technology systems created in recent years is to facilitate communication between dogs, their owners, and occasionally other living things. In an effort to comprehend canine behavior, emotional states, or health indications and convert them into information that is useful to humans, these systems include interactive platforms, wearable technology, and training aids. Instead of proposing a new system, this paper provides a narrative review of earlier studies on dog-human communication in the literature on animal-computer interaction and human-computer interaction. The review looks at the development of these technologies, their applications, and the difficulties in ensuring animal welfare, usability, and dependability. There is also discussion of ethical issues and possible dangers related to a growing reliance on technology. By synthesising prior research and design approaches, this paper aims to support current practices and encourage future exploration in technology-mediated communication between dogs and their owners.

KEYWORDS

Animal-computer interaction, Human-computer interaction, Dog-human interaction, Animal technology

1 INTRODUCTION

Humans connect with animals in a variety of ways and on a variety of levels. We do, in fact, live in an "animal's world," in the notion that our lives are inextricably linked to the lives of animals. This also implies that animals, such as the dogs we typically refer to as our pets live in a "human's world" in the sense that it is we, not them, who define and regulate our interactions with them to a great extent. The fact is we prefer to think of our pets as man's best friend. Dogs have been around longer than any other domestic species. They, more than any other species, embody the function of companion animals. Unfortunately, communicating with pets is difficult since humans and pets do not share the same language. Conventionally, vocal orders, body language, and behavioral clues are used to communicate with dogs and their owners. However, all approaches have limits, particularly when attempting to comprehend the emotional condition or particular demands of a dog. Several questions occur when it comes to communicating with dogs. For example, how do you keep a dog under control while the owner is not present? How can you spot a dog trained to perform certain behaviors in a given situation? What does this connection seem like from the dogs' point of view? How do they perceive the people with whom they interact? What responsibilities and duties result from our common understanding, attachment, and ostensibly "special" bonds with them? Is there an ethical implication, maybe

even an ethical implication that goes beyond animal welfare? To improve understanding of dogs and better meet their requirements, new technological innovations have brought about a variety of devices designed to help improve communication between owners and their canines. This paper adopts a narrative review approach to examine how dog-human communication technologies have evolved, what purposes they serve, and what challenges they raise for reliability, usability, and animal welfare.

2 BACKGROUND & PREVIOUS WORK

Dog communication is the term used to describe the information sharing that occurs between canines and people [4, 12]. Dog owners have long had difficulty comprehending the needs, feelings, and behaviors of their pets. In the past, voice orders, body language, and behavioral clues have all been used to communicate with dogs. Dogs are adept at learning human cues through training, while humans interpret canine signals through observation and experience. Dog communication behaviors are divided into two categories: visual and verbal. Humans may communicate with dogs in a number of ways. This includes, in general, vocalization, hand signaling, body position, and touch. Nevertheless, human interpretation is fallible and subject to bias, thus this approach has its limitations. In response to these difficulties, [10, 11] scientists have created a range of tools that aim to improve dogs' emotional and physical states through objective, data-driven insights into communication. A variety of technologies are utilized by these devices, such as microphones for vocalization analysis, sensors for physiological signal monitoring, and machine learning algorithms for behavioral pattern interpretation. [1]

This paper is not just concerned with household dogs, but also with dogs employed for training. Also on pets who are left at home alone by their owners. Owners are increasingly turning to technology to improve their pets' lives through training and support, entertainment, and biometric monitoring [14]. Technologies that enable human-dog remote connection are frequently created to relieve loneliness, boredom, or separation anxiety in home-alone dogs [6, 13]. The goal is to provide a more accurate understanding of a dog's needs and emotions, facilitating better care and interaction. They provide a variety of tasks, including voice communication, medication distribution, and live video [3, 7]. With the advancement of technology, capabilities such as video chat are often utilized to communicate with loved ones who are in different areas socially. Because dogs have such a deep impact on their humans' lives, it's no wonder that people want the ability to interact with their pets from a distance using technology as well.

Animal technology is still in its early stages of development. Several items that have been localized have begun to come on the market. In his paper, Germain Lemasson[9] and his team were interested in assistance dogs and began their work in collaboration with the French organization Handi'Chien, which has trained over 1,000 canines in the last 20 years. These canines undergo a two-year training process, starting with six months with a foster family to learn basic commands. They then spend 18 months at specialized institutes to learn fifty instructions before being placed with a new owner free of charge. Potential owners are assessed and given basic training on canine care. However, issues may arise with communication, which can be addressed with a robotic device acting as an intermediary between the dog and the owner. As the relationship between dogs and humans becomes more important in today's culture, the desire to stay connected to pets from afar has sparked interest in how technology may be utilized to strengthen that bond. Alexandre Pongrácz Rossi[17] and her team attempted to solve this issue by having a trainer and his canine demonstrate the capacity of a canine to respond accurately to verbal instructions delivered through video chat via Skype. Many individuals choose companion animals for companionship. However, due to most pet owners' hectic work schedules providing full-time care to the pet is very difficult.

To address the aforementioned issue, Yung-Sheng Shih[18] and the team wanted to create an intelligent and interactive system that would make a connection between the pet and the pet owner utilizing the Linux operating system and the Raspberry Pi board as a development platform. They suggested the method that provides the pet owner with a smartphone application that allows real-time connection with the pet over the internet. Alper Bozkurt[2] and his team shed some light on the new wearable technology they are working on which is expected to bridge the communication gap between people and their canine pals. It is equipped with physiological and behavioral sensors and is intended to provide owners with a real-time image of their dog's mental and emotional condition, allowing them to send back signals and orders more efficiently even while their dog is out of sight. Leaving a dog home alone is a common occurrence for many dog owners, with research showing that the relationship between dogs and their owners impacts the behavior of the dog. In their paper, the author[19] to explore the connection between the dog-owner relationship, the physical activity of the dog, and emotional experiences during separation and reunion. Nineteen dog owners had their dogs wear activity trackers for 2 weeks and filled out questionnaires regarding their relationship and their dog's behavior.

The results showed that a strong emotional bond between a dog and its owner can positively influence the dog's daily physical activity levels. Further research is needed to fully understand how these factors impact the welfare of dogs. For thousands of years, dogs have been human companions, enhancing communication and socialization. A review explored technology enabling intentional communication between humans and dogs without physical contact. Wearable devices, vibrotactile actuators, and video chats were commonly used methods[16]. In recent years, technology has allowed humans to connect with pets from a distance. In their paper,

the author[5] explores creating a video call device for dogs to contact their owners, giving animals control over technology.[15] created an alarm system for assistance dogs to seek help from owners in emergencies.

3 CONCEPTUAL TAXONOMY OF DOG-HUMAN COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

The reviewed literature shows that dog-human communication technologies generally fall into groups based on their primary sensing methods, interaction modes, and intended uses. Instead of introducing a new framework, this section brings together common design patterns found in current systems and sorts them into key categories.

Across the reviewed work, these categories often overlap. Many systems combine sensing, remote communication, and training functions within a single device. However, separating them into groups helps clarify their main design focus and makes it easier to understand the different goals that guide their development.

3.1 Wearable and Physiological Sensing Technologies

Much of the research looks at wearable devices with sensors that track a dog's body and behavior. These devices measure things like heart rate, temperature, posture, or movement to help owners understand their dog's emotional or physical state. For example, Bozkurt et al. [2] describe a harness with sensors for working and search-and-rescue dogs. Shih et al. [18] also study IoT-based systems that let owners monitor pets remotely using sensor-equipped devices linked to smartphones.

In these systems, canine signals are converted into data that can be interpreted by humans. Although these systems increase the amount of information that can be sent between dogs and their owners, they also present problems with signal interpretation, dependability, and contextual ambiguity.

This approach is part of a larger movement in human-animal interaction monitoring that is data-driven. The goal of designers is to lessen uncertainty in the interpretation of canine behavior by converting physical cues into quantifiable data. However, physiological markers don't always precisely reflect emotional experiences. The environment, stress, or individual differences in dogs can all affect sensor results. Therefore, owners must continue to use caution when evaluating the data provided by these technologies.

3.2 Remote Communication and Telepresence Systems

Another group of systems lets dogs and owners interact from a distance. These include video chat platforms, audio command systems, and devices that give treats remotely. For example, Rossi et al. [17] studied if dogs respond to verbal commands given over video calls. Other research looks at ways for owners to give treats or sounds from afar to keep their dogs engaged when apart.

These systems place an immense value on two-way communication, giving dogs stimulus and reinforcement while enabling humans to give directions and monitor reactions. However, their heavy reliance on training and contextual adaptation raises concerns regarding long-term behavioral impacts and the accuracy of interpretation.

Nevertheless, physical signs do not always correctly reflect emotional experiences. Variables like the environment, stress, or individual differences among dogs can affect sensor results. Therefore, when evaluating the information provided by these technologies, owners must continue to exercise caution.

3.3 Training and Assistance-Oriented Technologies

Some technologies are made for assistance or working dogs. These often use touch, sound, or environmental feedback to help dogs perform tasks in situations like emergency response or mobility help. Lemasson et al.[9] tested prototypes that help assistance dogs and their handlers communicate, using different types of signals to send commands and track activity.

In these cases, communication devices are not just helpful tools but are key parts of how people and dogs work together. This makes accuracy, quick response, and ethical responsibility especially important.

Minor misunderstandings can have significant consequences in professional settings. Therefore, usability and dependability must be considered when designing devices utilized in rescue or aid situations. However, the nature of trust between dogs and their handlers may change as a result of increased technological mediation. The way these technologies encourage collaboration without compromising the dog's autonomy or wellbeing must be taken into account by the designers.

3.4 Experimental and Speculative ACI Systems

A smaller but growing area in animal-computer interaction looks at experimental systems that ask how dogs might start interactions on their own. Projects like dog-activated video call systems [5] challenge the usual one-way communication by letting animals have some control over the technology.

These experimental systems add to wider discussions in ACI about agency, participation, and designing with animals in mind. Instead of just monitoring or controlling, they explore how technology can support new ways for dogs to interact that respect their abilities and viewpoints.

These initiatives are frequently exploratory in nature rather than focused on making money. Their worth comes from challenging preconceived notions about control and communication. Researchers expand the conversation from observation to engagement by looking at how dogs could start interactions. In the field of animal-computer interaction, this change promotes a more animal-centered perspective.

4 DISADVANTAGES OF THESE DEVICES

Despite their potential benefits, dog-human communication technologies present several limitations. First, many systems require a period of adaptation. Dogs may need time to become accustomed to wearable devices or remote communication tools, and improper use may lead to discomfort or device damage [8, 11, 20].

There is still concern about technical limits. Sensor-based systems might generate inadequate or erroneous data, especially when individual differences or the environment influence physiological outcomes. Owners' reactions to their dogs may be impacted by misinterpreting signals, particularly in situations where exact communication is crucial.

Additionally, an excessive dependence on technology could alter traditional patterns of connection. If technology mediation replaces in-person participation and observation, significant social cues may be overlooked. Designers must therefore consider how new platforms complement rather than replace conventional communication techniques.

Lastly, more general ethical concerns are raised by prolonged use of electronics and the growing use of monitoring technology in animal care. Although research in this area is still in its infancy, careful consideration of the advantages and disadvantages is required to make sure that these technologies enhance rather than jeopardize animal welfare.

5 CONCLUSION

An important development in our knowledge of and ability to connect with pets is the development of communication devices for dogs and their owners. With the help of these technologies, owners and their dogs may live better lives by understanding their emotions and behavior in new ways. Although there are many advantages, there are also issues that must be resolved with regard to accuracy, expense, and ethical issues. In order to maintain a positive and healthy human-dog relationship, it is imperative to balance the usage of these gadgets with more conventional forms of engagement.

6 FUTURE WORK

Subsequent investigations in this domain ought to concentrate on enhancing the precision and dependability of these apparatuses, specifically concerning the interpretation of heterogeneous canine signals originating from several breeds and individual canines. In-depth research is also required on the ethical ramifications of using these gadgets as well as their long-term effects on the human-dog bond. Expanding the variety of dog owners who can benefit from these technologies may be possible by creating more accessible and cheaper solutions. The quality of life for dogs and their owners may be further improved by investigating the integration of these gadgets with other smart home systems, which could offer a more comprehensive approach to pet management.

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